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Numerical simulation and experimental validation of ultrafast laser ablation on aluminum

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a numerical study of the ultrashort single pulse ablation process in aluminum has been conducted using the two-temperature model, taking into consideration the several dependencies of the parameters on temperature. The evolution of temperatures for each point within the material over time is obtained, allowing to comprehend the distribution of energy in the laser-metal interaction and its subsequent diffusion within the material. This study allows to gain a more precise understanding of the thermophysical and optical properties throughout the material heating and ablation process. The ablation process has been experimentally validated using a femtosecond laser on a polished aluminum film for a wide range of fluences. The developed theoretical model and the experimental values are in good agreement for both ablation depth and diameter across the entire range of powers studied, enabling reliable determination of the threshold fluence, laser spot size and material absorption coefficient. These parameters are crucial for achieving optimal micromachining processes.

1. Introduction

The study of the interaction between laser and metal has gained prominence in recent decades, owing to ultrashort pulses ($< 10\text{ps}$) based on the chirped amplification technique [1] and high peak power. This pulse offers certain advantages over longer pulses or continuous lasers since energy is deposited more rapidly into the material, achieving higher precision in processing by avoiding the undesirable heat accumulation effect [2]. Femtosecond ablation has already demonstrated its advantages in various fields, such as micro-nano machining [3], including the creation of laser-induced periodic surface structure (LIPSS) [4], additive manufacturing [5], surface structuring [6], and texturing [7] among other types of precise micromachining [8]. The relaxation time for metals is in the order of picoseconds, and the duration of the laser pulse is in femtoseconds. Therefore, the material will be in a state of high non-equilibrium, and the Fourier heat diffusion model cannot be used. So, in order to model ablation, we need to understand why it occurs, and for this purpose, various models have been proposed [9]. For metals, the dominant mechanism for material removal is phase explosion [10]; when the material temperature approaches the critical temperature of the thermodynamic equilibrium, the metal will be ablated [11]. Both the two-temperature model (TTM) [12] and molecular

dynamics simulation (MD) [13] employ this mechanism to explain ablation. The energy distribution in the process is divided into three stages. The first stage involves the absorption of the laser energy through photon-electron interactions. The other two stages are closely related, with one being the distribution in the bulk material through electron-phonon coupling, and the other the diffusion within the metal, facilitated by electronic, and, to a lesser extent, phonon lattice thermal conductivity. The TTM has been studied for various metals. However, in many cases, parameters are treated as constants, without considering their temperature dependencies, which can lead to misleading conclusions. In this article, a two-temperature model has been developed, considering the temperature dependencies of all parameters, to calculate the evolution of electronic and phonon temperatures using the finite difference method. This approach allows to obtain an ablation zone, where a portion of the material is removed, forming a crater. Simulations have been conducted at different laser powers to study how the fluence affects the process and to extract key ablation parameters. The same processes have been carried out experimentally, revealing a strong agreement between them. This comparison has yielded robust values for threshold fluence, absorption coefficient and spot size, which are critical for the proper material processing.

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Fig. 1. Mesh geometry & boundary conditions.

Table 1

Mesh, aluminum & laser parameters for $t = 0$, $T_{e,l} = 300$ K

Parameter (unit)	Value
Mesh	
dz (nm)	5
z (μm)	2
dx (nm)	25
x (μm)	15
dt (fs)	0.25
t (ps)	20
Aluminum	
C_e ($\text{J}/(\text{m}^3\text{K})$)	$2.3 \cdot 10^4$
C_l ($\text{J}/(\text{m}^3\text{K})$)	$2.4 \cdot 10^6$
K_e ($\text{W}/(\text{mK})$)	178.0
K_l ($\text{W}/(\text{mK})$)	1.8
G ($\text{J}/(\text{m}^3\text{Ks})$)	$2.5 \cdot 10^{17}$
R	0.91
δ (nm)	7.2
δ_b (nm)	11.4
T_c (K)	6700
Laser	
w_0 (μm)	10
t_p (fs)	280
λ (nm)	1032

2. Numerical modelling

2.1. Mesh model

The simulation is performed in 2D thanks to the rotational symmetry of the ablation process. In addition, the axial symmetry of the Gaussian laser beam allows halving the meshing using the axisymmetric boundary condition, as shown in Fig. 1. The laser absorption starts at $z = 0$ and propagates at positive z values. Null flux condition is applied at the right, upper and lower boundary. For the top surface, the thermal radiation condition is used but it is negligible [14], and the left boundary has the axisymmetric condition. Ambient temperature T_0 is fixed at 300 K.

$$T_e(r, z, t_0) = T_l(r, z, t_0) = T_0 \quad (1)$$

$$\left. \frac{\partial T_e}{\partial n} \right|_{\Omega} = \left. \frac{\partial T_l}{\partial n} \right|_{\Omega} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$q_{rad}|_{z=sur} = \sigma \varepsilon (T_{sur}^4 - T_0^4) \quad (3)$$

where Ω represents the boundary surfaces of the aluminum, σ is the

Stefan-Boltzmann constant and ε is the emissivity. T_{sur} is the ion temperature at $z = 0$.

2.2. Two-Temperature model

The two-temperature model proposed by Anisimov [15] is commonly used to describe interactions between ultrafast laser pulses and metallic materials:

$$C_e \frac{\partial T_e}{\partial t} = \nabla[\kappa_e \nabla T_e] - G(T_e - T_l) + Q \quad (4)$$

$$C_l \frac{\partial T_l}{\partial t} = \nabla[\kappa_l \nabla T_l] + G(T_e - T_l), \quad (5)$$

where the subscripts e and l refer to the electron and lattice parameters respectively, C is the heat capacity, T is the temperature, κ is the conductivity and G is the electron-lattice coupling factor. The laser pulse energy absorption is described within the source term Q , where the intensity varies in a spatiotemporal component as follows [16]:

$$Q(r, z, t) = S(r, z)T(t), \quad (6)$$

where the spatial contribution is defined as:

$$S = \frac{1-R}{\delta_{eff}} F \frac{w_0^2}{w^2} \exp\left(-\int_{z_s}^z \frac{1}{\delta} dz - \frac{2r^2}{w^2}\right), \quad (7)$$

Laser absorption from the surface into the bulk metal follows Lambert-Beers law.

Here, R is the reflectance of the metal, $\delta_{eff} = \delta + \delta_b$, where δ is the optical penetration on the aluminum film and δ_b is the ballistic length [17]; F is the laser fluence, w_0 is $1/e^2$ radius of the laser spot, and to take account for the small spatial extent after laser drilling, the laser fluence becomes position dependent with $w(z)$:

$$w(z) = w_0 \left(1 + \frac{z^2}{z_R^2}\right)^{(1/2)} \quad (8)$$

where z_R is the Rayleigh range:

$$z_R = \frac{n\pi w_0^2}{\lambda}, \quad (9)$$

z_s indicates where the absorption is taking place, in our case $z_s = 0$.

The temporal contribution has the following form:

$$T(t) = \sqrt{\frac{4\ln 2}{\pi t_p^2}} \exp\left(-2.77 \left(\frac{t - 2t_p}{t_p}\right)^2\right) \quad (10)$$

with t_p the full width at half maximum (FWHM) pulse duration, reaching its peak when $t = 2t_p$.

All the parameters present in Eqs. (4) and (5) vary with temperature. However, in some articles, all these dependencies are omitted, and constant values used. In other papers, only some relationships are considered. In this article, we have incorporated all temperature dependencies into the model. This can be seen in detail in Appendix A. *Temperature Dependences*. Knowing the evolution of both temperatures can accurately predict the ablation profile in the metal. It is well-known that if the lattice temperature is higher than 0.9 times the critical thermodynamic temperature [18–20] the material will be removed. For aluminum this value is $T_c = 6700$ K [21]. This is because such a high temperature results in an extremely high pressure that will be released through the adiabatic expansion in the ablated region [22].

To get an idea of the parameters, Table 1. provides them at the initial time of the simulation. We employ the finite difference method to solve Eqs. (4)-(5) at each grid point, updating the parameters at each time step based on these calculated temperatures.

The mesh values are selected with the consideration that depth

Fig. 2. Evolution of laser pulse, lattice and electron temperatures for several laser fluences a) 0–2 ps and b) 0–20 ps. T_e and T_l x-z planes, respectively, for a fluence of 1 J/cm^2 and c) 0.8 ps and d) 10 ps.

accuracy is more critical than width, setting values that allow for simulations to be performed within an optimal computational time. The time step size is chosen based on the previous values to meet stability and consistency criteria [23]. Laser parameters are chosen to match the values presented in the experimental study.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Verification of simulation model

Various simulations have been conducted for fluences from 0.5 to 10 J/cm^2 . Fig. 2 illustrates the evolution of both temperatures and normalized laser pulse intensity at the central ablation point for several fluences. We can observe that at the time 100 fs both lattices remain cold, while the phonon lattice largely maintains its initial temperature. This is because, as we established in Eq. (4), the absorption of laser energy occurs through the electron lattice. At 0.8 ps , when the laser pulse ceases to be relevant, the electronic temperature reaches its maximum. From that point onwards, due to the coupling term (G), its temperature will begin to decrease, transferring heat to the phonon lattice, which will gradually heat up until both temperatures equalize at a timescale on the order of tens of picoseconds, achieving the thermal equilibrium. It is important to note that the increase in fluence results in a higher electronic temperature, although the time at which maximum electronic temperature is achieved remains approximately at 0.8 ps . On the other hand, the instant at which thermal equilibrium is reached will indeed vary. The higher the fluence, the longer it will take to reach equilibrium. It is also important to note that the phonon lattice temperature loses its physical significance beyond ablation.

3.2. Experimental work

To verify if the values obtained with TTM are well aligned with experimental results, single-pulse holes on polish aluminum have been produced. For this purpose, a diode-pumped ultrafast fibre laser system (*Amplitude Satsuma HP*) of $\lambda = 1032 \text{ nm}$ and 280 fs pulse duration, with a maximum average power of 10 W at a repetition rate of 500 kHz , has been used. The laser power and spot size were modified and controlled by the different modules of the micromachining setup (*LASEA LS-Lab*) to achieve a spot size of $20 \mu\text{m}$ ($w_0 = 10 \mu\text{m}$) and fluences ranging from 1 – 10 J/cm^2 .

In order to evaluate both the depth and diameter of the different holes, the samples were analysed by a 3D optical profiler (*Sensofar S Neox*).

As seen in Fig. 3, the inherent material irregularities, even with polished material, are a challenge for measurement. Therefore, for low fluences, both the diameter and depth values are obtained as the average of 8 measurements, aiming to achieve a more consistent value. For high fluences, 5 measurements are used.

3.3. Model validation

Both the depths and the ablation diameters of the craters obtained in the simulation and experimentally are shown in Fig. 4. We can observe that in both cases, the experimental results and the predictions by the model show an excellent agreement.

For the ablation depth, the difference between the two regimes, low intensity ablation and medium–high intensity ablation [24], can be differentiated with a change in the trend due to the emergence of

Fig. 3. Images of craters obtained with a laser fluence of $6\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$. a) 50x Objective. b) 150x Objective.

collisionless absorption [25]. The simulated results in the high regime are slightly lower than the ones obtained experimentally due to this type of absorption, which will be studied in depth in future works.

For the diameter values, once again, there is an agreement between the experimental and simulated values. In this case, the values predicted for high fluences are slightly higher than the real-world results. This is due the fact that, at such high fluences, a heat-affected zone appears in the material, leading to an undesirable damaged structure, reducing the ablation zone. Therefore, it will not be of interest to use high fluences for high precision processing [26]. Hence, from now on we will focus on the low fluence regime.

Both for depth and diameter ablation, we can observe a logarithmic trend with fluence. We can obtain a fit in both cases dependent on laser and material parameters. The condition for ablation depth is given by the following expression [27]:

$$\text{Depth} = \delta \ln(F/F_{Th}), \quad (11)$$

where F_{Th} is the minimum fluence for ablation. where δ is the optical penetration depth. For diameter we have the approximation [28]:

$$\text{Diameter}^2 = 2w_0^2 \ln(F/F_{Th}) \quad (12)$$

where we again recover the threshold fluence and verify the spot size.

The parameters for the low regime have been retrieved by performing the corresponding fits provided by Eqs. (11)-(12) for both the model results and experimental data, and are displayed in Table 2:

For the parameters shown in the table, for low regime δ is nearly identical between the one proposed by the model and the experimental results and literature [29]. This value allows us to predict ablation depths with greater accuracy and it will be very helpful when studying multi-pulse processes [30]. The w_0 value is the expected, indicating that the approximation show in Eq. (12) is valid. In all the fits, we obtain a value of $F_{Th} \approx 0.5\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$ that is also in good agreement with the literature [29]. This value allows to obtain the optimal fluence value for material processing using the $F_{opt} = F_{th}e^2$ [26].

Fig. 4. Experimental and simulation results for ablation. a) Depth and b) Diameter².

Table 2
Parameters obtained by experimental and simulation fits.

Depth Fit			
Experimental		Model	
δ (nm)	F_{th} (J/cm ²)	δ (nm)	F_{th} (J/cm ²)
98.25	0.5	95.66	0.49
Diameter Fit			
Experimental		Model	
w_0 (μ m)	F_{th} (J/cm ²)	w_0 (μ m)	F_{th} (J/cm ²)
9.69	0.5	9.97	0.53

4. Conclusions

The ablation of aluminum using a femtosecond laser has been studied, both theoretically with a 2D axisymmetric two temperature model accounting for temperature dependencies, and experimentally for a low and medium fluence regime. A description of the ablation process has been provided, taking into consideration the thermodynamic critical temperature, optical absorption coefficient, ballistic length and collisionless absorption. These factors capture the several absorption mechanisms in metal. We have obtained both experimental and simulated results of the depth and the diameter of the craters, both in excellent agreement with each other and with literature [29,31]. For fluence values between 0.5–5 J/cm², we have obtained ablation parameters that allow to predict the expected depth and diameter of the ablation. For medium–high regime, an approximation is also obtained; however, collisionless absorption needs to be further investigated in

Appendix A. . Temperature dependences

In our study, we will include all dependencies on the electronic and ionic temperatures to obtain a model that closely resembles the actual physical process occurring during the ablation.

A.1. Optical and thermophysical temperature dependences

By incorporating both the Drude model and the Fresnel equations, we can calculate the variation of R and α with temperature and wavelength λ . The equation for the complex dielectric in the Drude model [32]:

more detail.

The presented results contribute to a theoretical understanding of aluminum ablation with ultrafast laser, as well as to the optimization of the process, with potential application extending to other materials as well.

5. Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

Statement: During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT in order to improve readability and language. After using this tool, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take (s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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$$\epsilon = \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2 = \epsilon_\infty - \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega(\omega + i\gamma_D)} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where $\epsilon_\infty = 8.5116$ is the aluminum dielectric constant. Laser frequency is $\omega = 2\pi c/f$, $\omega_p = \sqrt{n_e e^2/m_e \epsilon_0}$ is the plasma frequency [33]. γ_D is the damping coefficient,

The scattering rate in this model is given by the sum of the electron–electron scattering rate $1/\tau_{e-e} = AT_e^2$, and the electron phonon scattering rate $1/\tau_{e-ph} = BT_I$. By definition, the damping coefficient is equal to the reciprocal of electron relaxation time τ_e .

$$\tau_e = \frac{1}{A_e T_e^2 + B_I T_I} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

A_e and B_I are assumed constants for Aluminum [34].

The complex refractive index is derived from the real and imaginary parts of the complex dielectric function, which is given by:

$$f = n + ik \quad (\text{A.3})$$

n is the normal refractive index and k is the extinction coefficient. These values are obtained from:

$$n = \sqrt{\left(\epsilon_1 + \sqrt{\epsilon_1^2 + \epsilon_2^2}\right)}/2 \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$k = \sqrt{\left(-\epsilon_1 + \sqrt{\epsilon_1^2 + \epsilon_2^2}\right)}/2 \quad (\text{A.5})$$

With all this information, we can retrieve the values from R and α for each instant using Fresnel equations [35]:

$$R = \frac{(n-1)^2 + k^2}{(n+1)^2 + k^2} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$\alpha = 2\omega k/c \quad (\text{A.7})$$

The value of the optical penetration depth is obtained by taking the reciprocal of absorption coefficient, $\delta = 1/\alpha$. Additionally, the contribution of ballistic length [36] will have to be considered in our study:

$$\delta_{bal} = v_F \tau_e, \quad (\text{A.8})$$

With these two values we can retrieve the absorption coefficient α_{eff} as:

$$\delta_{eff} = \delta + \delta_{ball}. \quad (\text{A.9})$$

Furthermore, due to the fluence regimes in which we work, there will also be electron absorption without any collision, this phenomenon is called collisionless absorption [37]. Based on the experimental and theoretical study of absorption [38], we have recalculated the reflectance ($R = 1 - A$) value, distinguishing between the regime where collisionless absorption is negligible and where it is not, as can be seen in Fig. A.1. Relative Absorption vs. Fluence.

Fig. A1. Relative Absorption vs. Fluence.

A.2. Thermophysical properties

With ultrashort laser pulses, we must differentiate between electron and ion lattice. Consequently, each of their properties will exhibit specific dependences based on their respective temperatures, or both.

The value of the electronic heat capacity is usually obtained by using the Sommerfeld expansion $C_e(T_e) = \gamma T_e$. However, this model is not valid for high temperatures, so we have to use the derivative of the electron energy density with respect to temperature [39].

$$C_e(T_e) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\partial f(\varepsilon, \mu, T_e)}{\partial T_e} g(\varepsilon) \varepsilon d\varepsilon \quad (\text{A.10})$$

where $f(\varepsilon, \mu, T_e)$ is the Fermi distribution function, $f(\varepsilon, \mu, T_e) = \{\exp((\varepsilon - \mu)/k_B T_e) + 1\}^{-1}$, $g(\varepsilon)$ is the electron density of states (DOS) at the energy level ε , μ is the chemical potential at T_e .

The phonon heat capacity can be calculated from quantum treatment [40]:

$$C_i(T_i) = 2n_a \left(\frac{\partial \langle \varepsilon_p \rangle}{\partial T_i} \right)_V \quad (\text{A.11})$$

This model is a good fit for low-temperature regime; however, as the temperature increases, it does not reflect well the dependence [41]. Due to this, we have employed the Shomate equation, distinguishing between solid and liquid phase as well [42]:

$$C_i(T_i) = A + Bt + Ct^2 + Dt^3 + E/t^2, \quad (\text{A.12})$$

where $t = T_i/1000$. The thermal conductivity in metals is dominated by the electronic contribution; but, ion thermal conduction plays a key role in the ultrafast phase change. Therefore, we must take it into account.

The electron thermal conductivity is derived using the Drude theory for metals [39]:

$$\kappa_e = \frac{1}{3} v_F^2 \tau_e C_e, \quad (\text{A.13})$$

where v_F is the Fermi velocity and τ_e is the electron relaxation time.

The ion thermal conductivity is approximately 1% of the overall thermal conductivity [43],

$$\kappa_i \approx \kappa_e / 99, \quad (\text{A.14})$$

The coupling factor is calculated as follows [44]:

$$G = \frac{\pi \hbar k_B \lambda \langle \omega^2 \rangle}{g(\varepsilon_F)} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g^2(\varepsilon, T_e) \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial \varepsilon} \right) d\varepsilon \quad (\text{A.15})$$

where \hbar is the reduced Planck's constant, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, λ is the electron phonon coupling constant and $\langle \omega^2 \rangle$ is the second moment of the phonon spectrum.

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